

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

My Cult-Rural Toolkit

Research tools description

Call: H2020-SC5-2016-2017
Number: 776465

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465

1. Table of Contents

1. TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION	5
3. ABSTRACT	7
4. MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT	8
5. RESEARCH TOOLS DESCRIPTION (OBJECTIVE, USER INTERFACE)	8
5.1 MINI-LANDSCAPES	10
5.1.1 WORKSHOP OUTCOMES, DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE	12
5.2 OBJECT MAPPING	12
5.2.1 WORKSHOP OUTCOMES, DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE	14
5.3 WALKING MAPS	15
5.3.1 WORKSHOP OUTCOMES, DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE	17
5.4 RATE MY VIEW (RMV)	17
5.4.1 BACK END DASHBOARD.....	19
5.4.2 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION.....	21
5.4.3 DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE.....	21
5.5 LANDSCAPE CONNECT	22
5.5.1 USER INSTRUCTIONS OF MOBILE APPLICATION.....	23
5.5.2 RESEARCHERS – WRITING QUESTIONNAIRES	24
5.5.3 RESEARCHER – MANAGING COLLECTED DATA	25
5.5.4 FACILITATOR – WORKSHOP FORMAT EXAMPLE.....	26
5.5.5 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION.....	27
5.5.6 DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE.....	27
5.6 SOCIAL MEDIA TOOLS	28
5.6.1 DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE	28
6. TRAINING AND COMMUNICATION	28
6.1 TRAINING FOR USING PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOP METHODS	28
6.2 TRAINING FOR USING GEO-SPATIAL INFORMATION MANAGERMENTS METHODS (APPS)	29
6.3 COMMUNICATION WITH THE COMMUNITIES	29
7. DATA GATHERING STRATEGY	30
7.1 PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOP METHODS	31
7.2 PARTICIPATORY GEO-SPATIAL INFORMATION MANAGERMENTS METHODS	31
7.3 SOCIAL MEDIA MONITORING TOOLS	32
7.4 DATA ANALYSIS STRATEGY	32
8. ANNEX I RATE MY VIEW DATABASE STRUCTURE	33

9.	<u>ANNEX II LANDSCAPE CONNECT DATABASE STRUCTURE</u>	<u>38</u>
10.	<u>ANNEX III MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT – AN INTRODUCTION TO THE PHYSICAL TOOLS.....</u>	<u>45</u>
11.	<u>ANNEX IV MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT – POCKET PHOTO GUIDE</u>	<u>50</u>
12.	<u>ANNEX V MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT – OBJECT MAPPING FACILITATOR GUIDE</u>	<u>53</u>
13.	<u>ANNEX VI MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT – WALKING MAPS FACILITATOR GUIDE.....</u>	<u>62</u>
14.	<u>ANNEX VII MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT – MINI-LANDSCAPES FACILITATOR GUIDE.....</u>	<u>71</u>
15.	<u>ANNEX VII MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT – RATE MY VIEW FACILITATOR GUIDE.....</u>	<u>80</u>
16.	<u>ANNEX V MY CULT-RURAL TOOLKIT – LANDSCAPE CONNECT FACILITATOR GUIDE.....</u>	<u>89</u>

List of Figures

Figure 4.1. Cultural ecosystem services framework.....	8
Figure 5.1. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 1: Gathering and greeting	10
Figure 5.2. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 2 – Building landscapes in smaller groups	11
Figure 5.3. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 3 – Set open questions (record open data).....	11
Figure 5.4. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 4 – Close workshop	12
Figure 5.5. Object Mapping participatory workshop. Step 1 - Greeting and Setting up the scene.	13
Figure 5.6. Object Mapping participatory workshop. STEP 3 - Building the landscape.	13
Figure 5.7. Object Mapping participatory workshop. STEP 4 - Coming back to personal objects.	14
Figure 5.8. Walking Maps participatory workshop. Step 2 – The walk	16
Figure 5.9. Walking Maps participatory workshop. Step 2 – The walk	16
Figure 5.10 RmV the “My View” screen	18
Figure 5.11 RmV the “Around Me” screen.....	18
Figure 5.12 Rate My View – Dashboard view.....	19
Figure 5.13 Rate My View – Areas screen	19
Figure 5.14 Rate My View – Views screen.....	19
Figure 5.15 Rate My View – Download view.....	20
Figure 5.16 Rate My View – Edit view	20
Figure 5.17 Rate My View – Hide from public view	20
Figure 5.18 Landscape Connect – user view; (a) questionnaires menu; (b)quick code view; (c) add from code view.	23
Figure 5.19 Landscape Connect – questionnaire view (multiple pages).....	24
Figure 5.20 Landscape Connect –publishing questionnaire view.	25
Figure 5.21 Landscape Connect –publishing questionnaire view.	25
Figure 5.23 Landscape Connect – data analysis: word cloud view.	26
Figure 7.1 Data collection points for co-monitoring activities using My Cult-Rural Toolkit.	30

List of Tables

Table 1: Revision History	5
Table 2: Acronyms used	6
Table 7.1 The use of the participatory workshop methods in the Ruritage co-monitoring process.	31
Table 7.2 The use of the participatory geo-spatial information management methods in the Ruritage co-monitoring process.....	32
Table 7.3 The use of the social media monitoring tools in the Ruritage co-monitoring process.	32

2. Background Information

Table 1: Revision History

Project Full title	Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
Project Acronym	RURITAGE	
Grant Agreement No.	776465	
Coordinator	University of Bologna (UNIBO)	
Project start date and duration	June 2018 – May 2022 (48 months)	
Project website	www.ruritage.eu	
Deliverable Nr.	5.2	29/11/2019
Work Package No	5	
Work Package Title	RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem	
Responsible	UoP	
Author(s)	J Martin, K Łuczniak, D Williamson, A Guy	
Contributor(s)	C De Luca, S Tondelli UNIBO	
Reviewer(s) (if applicable)	Name, surname; name, surname Acronym of organisation	
Status:	Final (F)	●
	Draft (D)	
	Revised draft (RV)	
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)	●
	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (CO)	

Table 2: Acronyms used

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Intervention Area
CNH	Cultural and natural heritage
RmV	Rate My View
LC	Landscape Connect

3. Abstract

The two key objectives of the Ruritage Co-Monitoring Programme (Task4.4) are to document the impact of actions designed to enhance the cultural heritage values investigated by the project and to give the communities within Replicator sites the ability to monitor and evaluate such actions beyond the life of the project.

The principles around monitoring such change are underpinned by the identification of the key benefits that can be derived from those cultural ecosystem services (CES) related to cultural heritage. These ecosystem services and their economic, social and environmental attributes will be identified through the Action Planning activity linked to Task 3.3. The community groups (local and visitors) initial values and perceptions of services will be recorded before the start of any actions linked to Task 3.3 and hence will form a baseline for the assessment of success. During the life of the project, monitoring and evaluation will then be carried out by the Replicator communities.

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit has been designed and developed to assist and build capacity within Replicator communities to complete these assessment tasks. The toolkit employs both ubiquitous technologies and community workshops, in order to extend the reach of engagement. The toolkit contains three levels of data gathering: participatory workshop methodologies banded Tagscape (Mini-Landscapes, Object Mapping and Walking Maps), participatory geo-spatial methods facilitated by two mobile phone (tablet) Apps ('RateMyView' and 'Landscape Connect'), and social media monitoring tools based on data mining techniques.

4. My Cult-Rural Toolkit

As indicators for evaluating and co-monitoring results of Ruritage actions in Replicator communities in terms of individual, social and cultural change we will focus on the identification the key benefits derived from those Cultural Heritage Ecosystem Services (CES) developed over the project lifespan. Cultural Ecosystem Services derive, in their turn, from interactions between people and their local natural environments through cultural practices. This approach emphasises that since place, locality, and landscape characteristics are often intertwined with cultural and social practices, consideration of the location (or context) is essential when monitoring the generation of cultural goods and benefits¹. Figure 4.1 describes graphically the complex relationships between different cultural, and environmental framework components that influence and are shaped by cultural ecosystem services, and their benefits.

Figure 4.1. Cultural ecosystem services framework.

Adapted from UK NEA Follow-on CES framework in Church et al. (2014).

In summary, the main purposes of the co-monitoring activities will be to gain a broader and deeper understanding of the varied ways that people interact with their environment, and draw benefits from those cultural ecosystem services that will be supported or developed through the development of Ruritage actions (Task 3.3). Methods for eliciting these indicators and metrics will draw upon the qualitative methodologies of the social sciences, and the arts and humanities.

5. Research Tools description (objective, user interface)

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit has been designed and developed to assist and build capacity within Replicator communities to assess the impact of locally driven actions. The toolkit employs both ubiquitous technologies and

¹ Church, A., Fish, R., Haines-Young, R., Mourato, S., Tratalos, J., Stapleton, L., & Willis, C. (2014). UK National Ecosystem Assessment follow-on: cultural ecosystem services and indicators.

community workshops, in order to extend the reach of engagement. The kit consists of three physical tools, two digital tools and a social media monitoring tool. The physical tools are: (1) Mini-Landscapes, (2) Object Mapping and (3) Walking Maps. The digital tools are: (4) Rate My View App and (5) Landscape Connect App. The tools can be accessed via the Ruritage platform (www.ruritage-ecosystem.eu/mycultruraltoolkit)

In addition to the five tools that will be used by the Replicators, a social media mining tool has been compiled for use by the research team. The results from this tool will be shared with the Replicators but they will not have access to the tool itself. This tool was not identified in the original proposal, however it is seen as an important addition to the project.

The PGIS tool that was identified in the original proposal was not developed as it was felt that it had become redundant because of the closer integration of the apps (Rate my View and Landscape Connect) and the Ruritage Atlas. During the development of the Atlas it became clear that the outputs from the apps could be integrated and displayed on the Atlas, hence providing a similar function to a PGIS system. This integration of the application also reduces the number of systems that a user needs to access and hence makes the experience a lot more efficient and user friendly.

Tools 1-3 of the toolkit focus on three bespoke participatory research tools that utilise local and raw materials to co-create temporary installations outside. During the co-creation, each tool stimulates discussion and once made, the installations are recorded using visual and qualitative methods. Tools 4-5 are mobile phone applications (apps) that are free to download and allow text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets.

My Cult-Rural Toolkit consists three categories of tools that aim to facilitate the measurement (or capture) of CES(heritage)-derived benefits to different groups of participants (stakeholders) in relation to landscape (features or locations):

- Participatory workshop methods emphasise local people's involvement in building knowledge and the understanding of the research area through collective enquiry, collaborative actions and shared reflection. These tools are in the form of hands-on workshops with small groups of local participants. The collected evidence is mostly of qualitative character. The researcher can expect to obtain a deep, qualitative understanding of the participants' unique experiences. Under the umbrella Tagscape brand, the Mini-Landscapes, Object Mapping and Walking Maps tools belong to this category.
- Participatory geo-spatial information management methods have the benefit of combining participatory research methods with geographic information systems (GIS) that allow mapping of the spatial distribution of cultural ecosystem services. Participants become expert in understanding and mapping their own experiences within the landscape. Two mobile phone or tablet-based applications (RateMyView and Landscape Connect) have been developed. Both record individual, subjective experiences using survey methods, with geo-spatial information. This category of tools allows researchers and participants to co-examine the interpersonal and spatial distribution of the perceived benefits of CES.
- Social media monitoring tools allow for the analysis of the view of the selected landscapes from a wider social perspective. People commonly share their views and opinions on-line by commenting, sharing pictures and interacting with each other hence such content provides rich contextual data. Our tools for analysing Twitter and Instagram activities allows Replicators to access and interpret the text and graphic data on how people perceive the landscape that includes or borders their geographic location.

5.1 Mini-Landscapes

The Mini-Landscapes method is a participatory workshopping activity that involves participants in creating a mini-landscape in an outdoor setting in the landscape. Participants are divided into groups of four or five and asked to explore the area and produce a mini-landscape in vivarium that represents the group's view of the area. As the task progresses facilitators ask open questions and discuss the process of mini-landscape construction. Towards the end of the task, participants answer the open questions by writing only one or two words upon glass slides, and then placing the slides into their mini-landscapes wherever they choose. The mini-landscapes and words are then documented by the facilitators (visually, and/or in transcription).

The Facilitator of the workshop follows five steps :

Step 1 – Gathering and greeting

- Welcome the whole participant group and introduce the purpose and plan for the workshop.
- Participants each introduce themselves with name and 1-3 sentence description of a place of personal significance or meaning (e.g. a favourite walk, viewpoint, secret place, etc.).
- One facilitator leads the whole group in short (10mins) familiarisation walk through the workshop landscape. During introduction be aware that what is said at this point might skew results collected later.

Figure 5.1. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 1: Gathering and greeting

Step 2 – Building landscapes in smaller groups

- Explain that five subgroups (of 2-3 people per vivarium) will each construct their own mini-landscape.
- Split the workshop into the 5 subgroups – some pairings might choose to work together.
- Ask each subgroup what kind of mini-landscape they think they might like to make (Vivariums can contain abstractions, simulations or more literal representations of the surrounding workshop landscape). Participants should be encouraged to discuss together what they would like to make.
- Explain that each subgroup has 1hr to collect and arrange materials to fill a vivarium with a mini-landscape.
- Explain that each subgroup can place their vivarium wherever they would like in the workshop terrain.
- Explain that facilitators will visit them as time proceeds to help or advise.
- Explain that during the making process each subgroup will be asked some questions about their mini landscape.

Figure 5.2. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 2 – Building landscapes in smaller groups

Step 3 – Set open questions (record open data)

- Once each subgroup is well on the way to making their vivarium (at least 1/2hr) give each person in the subgroups a set of 8 slides and a glass chalk pen.
- Whilst distributing slides and pens facilitators set a couple of open questions.
- Explain that questions are to be answered in only 1-2 words per slide, but that as many slides (answers) as desired can be made for each question.
- Encourage each subgroup to choose a few most significant slides they would like to display in or around their vivarium. (Participants are now self-coding the data).
- Spread the task of materials distribution and question-setting between the two facilitators.
- If there is a third facilitator they might be tasked with documenting the emerging mini-landscapes and participants in the process of making vivariums photographically, paying attention to capturing slide answers, especially those placed in and around vivariums.

Figure 5.3. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 3 – Set open questions (record open data)

Step 4 – Close workshop

- Move the vivariums close enough that they can all be seen together by whole group.
- Ask all the participants to examine and look into each of the 5 vivariums.
- Ask each subgroup to summarise their own mini-landscape to the whole workshop group.
- Allow an opportunity for discussion and shared thoughts about the workshop process.
- Encourage participants to make personal records (photos or notes) since mini-landscapes will be dismantled (See Visual Recording Tips: e.g. to get close-ups of the mini-landscapes participants could lie down if the ground is not wet or hard).
- Facilitators close workshop formally, and thank participants.

Figure 5.4. Mini-Landscape participatory workshop. Step 4 – Close workshop

5.1.1 Workshop outcomes, data collection and storage

The workshop produces a number of outcomes and research data that might be used to inform future change or decision-making processes in the communities:

- Physical data – materials collected to construct the mini-landscapes
- Qualitative data – recordings of the final mini-landscape presentations, discussions, and participants' slide responses.
- Visual data - photo documentation of the mini-landscapes.
- Spatial data – the placement of slides in relationship to the mini-landscapes.
- Mini-landscapes – participants' personal representations of the discussed landscape - a holistic, multimodal presentation of research findings.

The qualitative, visual and spatial data: the recorded group presentations, discussion, and photo documentation of the mini-landscapes and placement of slides within the landscapes will be collected by the Facilitator and submitted to the Ruritage SharePoint Site. Group presentations and discussion will also need to be transcribed and translated, then added to the provided spreadsheet together with related photo documentation. The principles of the Data Management Plan will be followed with all data sets.

Any additional data, physical data and built mini-landscapes are only temporary primary data and will not be stored following photo documentation. However, the mini-landscapes might be publicly displayed beyond the duration of workshop.

5.2 Object Mapping

The object mapping tool enables outdoor participatory workshops centred on reflective interaction between participants and their landscape. Participants are asked to bring an object related to their area that has particular meaning to them. At the start of the workshop the participants are divided into four groups and invited to create a diagrammatic landscape map using local materials and a grid. On completion of the map, participants are asked to video each other discussing their object. The exercise finishes with the participants mapping their object and again discussing its importance and its location in the map. The exercise involves both participants and facilitators in collecting and recording data.

The Facilitator of the workshop follows four steps:

Step 1 - Greeting and Setting up the scene

- Introduce the group to the general plan of the activity,
- Check that each participant has brought a personally meaningful object,
- Walk with your participants to the spot you have chosen to work in. If you have not set-up the basics of the diagram before arrival, now ask your participants to set this up. This can allow time

to think about the activity you have just explained.

- Ask two people to put down the rope, crossing the rope so it creates four segments and leaves the feeling of a circle around it.
- Ask two people to write on 8 tent pole pegs the following twice over: intangible, tangible.
- Request that four people write each of the following four topics on a tent label: Health & Wellbeing, Tourism, Sense of Place, and Aesthetic Appreciation. Ask them to hold on to the labels.
- Ask the remainder of people to each take a tote bag and trowel and then to 'take-in' the landscape around them for five minutes until the framework of the diagram is set-up.

Figure 5.5. Object Mapping participatory workshop. Step 1 - Greeting and Setting up the scene.

STEP 2 - Dividing into segments

- Ask the four people with the tent labels to each step forward and choose a segment of the circle, step into it, and hold up the topics that they have written.
- Ask the participants to join one of the segments until each segment contains a similar number of people.
- Allow the participants time for a short discussion about the topic they have chosen.

STEP 3 - Building the landscape

- Ask the participants to take 25 minutes out in the landscape searching for a single object in the landscape that as a group they feel represents the label in their segment. They can use the bags to collect these objects.
- When each group returns, ask them to fill their segment with their collected objects so that they form a quarter of a circle. If they have not collected enough material to do this, encourage them to collect more.
- Allow time for each group to present and discuss the material they have chosen. Photograph and make a note of what they are describing.

Figure 5.6. Object Mapping participatory workshop. STEP 3 - Building the landscape.

STEP 4 - Coming back to personal objects

- As soon as all the segments are filled, ask everyone to work in pairs, perhaps with someone they don't know.
- Ask them to stand around the outside of the circle with their partners.
- Then ask them to:
 - Share their objects with each other
 - Video each other saying in one or two sentences: What their object is and why they chose it?
 - Place their objects where they feel they fits on this map and film each other doing this so that it is clear where the object has been placed on the circular diagrammatic map
- -Ask if each participant can also take a photograph of the object on the grid
 - Now ask a few of the partner groups to share their discussions and thoughts about their objects for the whole group. Repeat until you feel the exercise has reached a good ending stage.

Figure 5.7. Object Mapping participatory workshop. STEP 4 - Coming back to personal objects.

Object Mapping data collation - After workshop

The facilitator records the following information:

- Photographs of the landscape without the personal objects included.
- Close-up photographs of each segment.
- A description of why each group choose the objects that they did.

The Facilitator should also check that the participants have captured the following and that they understand how to upload their material to the Ruritage SharePoint site:

- Photographs of personal objects.
- Recordings of interviews related to objects.
- Photographs of each segment with personal objects placed inside.
- Photographs of the whole landscape with the personal object included.

5.2.1 Workshop outcomes, data collection and storage

The workshop produces a number of outcomes and research data that might be used to inform future change or decision-making processes in the communities:

- Physical data – materials collected to fill segments and participants' personal objects
- Qualitative data – recording of the interviews carried out during the workshop.
- Visual data - photo documentation of the workshop.
- Spatial data – the placement of personal objects and related interviews in relationship to the landscape and grid categories.
- Built landscape – containing collected material and participants' personal objects - a holistic, multimodal representation of research findings.

The qualitative, visual and spatial data: video interviews and photo documentation of the landscape and personal objects placed in the grid will be collected by the Facilitator and submitted to the Ruritage SharePoint Site. Interviews will need to be transcribed and translated, then added to the provided spreadsheet together with related photo documentation. The principles of the Data Management Plan will be followed with all data sets.

Any additional data, physical data and the grid segments and objects are primary data and will not be stored after the photo documentation.

5.3 Walking Maps

The Walking Map tool enables participatory workshops centred on reflective interaction between participants and their environment. Groups of participants are invited to take a short walk around a chosen location and to collect materials and objects that catch their eye on the way. A facilitator walks with the group posing questions aimed at opening discussions (and stories) around the workshop topic in relation to the objects and features that have attracted the participants' attention. Answers are recorded in relation to the collected objects, and are accurately geo-located in relation to the walk path (using a mobile phone application – Landscape Connect). Once participants have completed the walk they create an installation/exhibition that reflects and connects the collected objects, the participants' responses, and the trace of the walk path.

Walking is used as a facilitation method to both encourage an interactive approach between participants and their surroundings beyond simple generalised description, and to invoke shared discursive and narrative reflections upon the questions that have been set by the facilitator along the walk path.

The Facilitator of the workshop follows five steps:

Step 1 – Gathering, greeting and setting up the walk

- Introduce the group to the general plan of the activity around a reflective walk and the general topic for the walk.
- The facilitator may hold an open discussion, but this should be kept short, the walk will further explore the topic.
- Decide together with participants whether to work as one group, or to break into smaller subgroups (each with its own facilitator).

Step 2 – The walk

- Participants themselves lead the walk and choose a path that will last no more than 45 minutes.
- The walk should end at a chosen final destination – the installation/exhibition place.
- If the walk involves subgroups then each should choose a different path.
- Ask participants to collect materials (appropriate to the topic) as they walk and to place them in their collecting bags.
- Also ask participants to number their bags as they stop and collect objects at each location along the walk path.

Figure 5.8. Walking Maps participatory workshop. Step 2 – The walk

Step 3 - Exploring the deeper meaning

- Once participants are walking and collecting materials, begin to ask open questions around the walk topic (See tips on open questions/data).
- For each question asked answers are recorded by the facilitator with the Landscape Connect mobile application. This allows accurate geo-location of each answer and cross-links it to the relevant numbered collection bag.
- Facilitators could also record emerging discussions, or make additional notes.

Step 4 - Setting up the exhibition

- Once the group (or subgroups) arrive at the final destination of the walk (the exhibition place) ask each participant (or group) to create a 'washing line' by tying strings to a tree or buildings.
- This might be a good opportunity to suggest a short break and drink.
- Ask participants to hang their filled collection bags on the 'washing line' using wooden pegs in their numbered collection order.
- Now add written summaries of answers that were recorded during the walk next to the related objects in their bag (using the recorded bag reference numbers).
- The group now discuss the collected material and related answers.
- This discussion could be recorded – but be aware that long recordings may lead to later transcription work.

Figure 5.9. Walking Maps participatory workshop. Step 2 – The walk

Step 5 – Documenting the installation/exhibition

- Encourage participants to take photographs of the installation and look at the 'washing lines' of other individuals/subgroups.
- The facilitator also now documents the objects on each line separately, including the related questions and answers.
- As appropriate the installation/exhibition can be left on view for the public in the original walk destination or transferred to another location.

5.3.1 Workshop outcomes, data collection and storage

The workshop produces a number of outcomes and research data that might be used to inform future change or decision-making processes in the communities:

- Physical data – materials collected on the walk,
- Qualitative data – recording of the interviews carried out during the walk,
- Visual data - photo documentation of collected materials and the exhibition.
- Spatial data – both, materials and interviews are recorded with the location.
- Exhibition – containing the collected materials, participants’ responses and the trace of their trail giving holistic, multimodal representation of research findings.

The qualitative data: interviews recording and photo documentation of exhibition and collected material, including the related questions and answers will be collected by the Facilitator and submitted to the Ruritage SharePoint Site. Interviews will need to be transcribe and translated, then added to the provided spreadsheet together with related photo documentation. Then the collected data will be analysed to reveal the place of CES and CES benefits in the context of the local landscape.

The spatial data (documented by Landscape Connect app, will be stored both on LC server and merge with qualitative set of data at the Ruritage SharePoint site, indicating the spatial dimensions of the CES and CES benefits revealed through qualitative data. The principles of the Data Management Plan will be followed with all data sets.

Any additional data, physical data and the final exhibition are only temporary primary data and will not be stored after photo documentation. However, the exhibition might be displayed beyond the duration of workshop.

5.4 Rate My View (RmV)

Rate My View is a mobile phone application (app) that allows in-the-field data collection, combined with a server-based back end that allows real-time data analysis. The app is free to download and allows text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets. It uses GPS technology to pinpoint the users location and also detects the direction the user is facing. Images and text are cached on user’s devices and then automatically uploaded to the Rate my View website when Wi-Fi or phone signal are available.

The app is very simple to operate. The app opens up to the “My View” screen (Figure 5.3.1 a,b) that allows the user to take a photo, rate their view (1-5 stars) and describe how the view makes them feel in three words or short phrases.

The user is also asked to indicate “How well you feel you know the area in your view?” using three options (“Not at all, Not very well, Very well”) and their age band in five options (0-18, 19-24, 25-44, 45-64, 65+).

Figure 5.10 RmV the “My View” screen

The user can also view other users’ rated views on a map using the “Around Me” screen. By clicking the green icons on the map the details of these submissions can be viewed. Figure 5.3.2.a-b.

Figure 5.11 RmV the “Around Me” screen.

5.4.1 Back end Dashboard

The application has a simple Dashboard to manage uploaded images and text.

Dashboard
 Login to **Dashboard** with web browser (Best with Google Chrome/Mozilla Firefox) at:
www.ratemyview.co.uk/admin
 The **Dashboard** gives an overview of recently submitted **views** in your **submission area** as statistics, and as map locations.
 Move between different back end **screens** with tabs.

Figure 5.12 Rate My View – Dashboard view

Areas
 The **Areas** screen shows all **submission areas** in the system.
 Click the right-hand side of the screen to change a submission area's **twitter handle** or **website address**.
 Hover the mouse over the icon at the bottom left of the screen to change the **baseman** between Terrain/Satellite layers.

Figure 5.13 Rate My View – Areas screen

Views
 The **Views** screen allows all submitted views in a **submission area** to be reviewed.
 To filter all views in a **submission area**, use the drop-down list in the **Search** box at top left of the views screen.
 Click any map to the left-hand side of each view to see the **map** of all views in this **submission area**.

Figure 5.14 Rate My View – Views screen

Download

Click the **Download** button at the top right of the views screen to download all **views** data from this submission area.

Data can be downloaded as Google Earth/GIS layer (.kmz file), images (.jpgs), or as data for use in Excel (.csv).

Figure 5.15 Rate My View – Download view

Edit View

To edit a submitted view, click on the image to the right-hand side of the **views** screen.

The **Edit View** screen will open.

This screen allows **moderators** to correct any view details (headings, spellings, etc.)

The exact GIS location marker **can be moved** in the edit view page. Click Location tab, then drag the GOS marker to a new position on the map/satellite view.

Figure 5.16 Rate My View – Edit view

Hide from Public

Moderators can temporarily **hide** any view from the public website should it contain content that violates the Terms of Service.

If necessary, these views can be **deleted** by the moderator.

To hide a view, click the **checkbox** near the bottom of the edit view screen.

Figure 5.17 Rate My View – Hide from public view

5.4.2 Technical specification

Database: MongoDB database system was used to develop Rate My View. MongoDB differs from traditional relational database systems as it is a document database - chiefly comprised of complex objects allowing a rich data object. MongoDB was selected since it allows very simple schema changes, only being enforced in application code and offers excellent geographical extensions. The software natively supports querying WGS84 lat/long points with complex queries, including geoWithin, allowing database-level support for enforcing geographical constraints on submissions areas.

Server: The server software is written in Node.js, the server-side framework for running JavaScript. It is a feature-complete software library and ecosystem for writing fast performant web servers. It supports third party libraries and allows fast-paced development. The server code runs on the Heroku platform, a hosted Platform as a Service (PaaS) system. This simplifies the maintenance of the system and supports very high uptime requirements since every part of the infrastructure is virtualised.

Interoperability: The Rate my View system uses a static set of questions programmed in the iOS and Android app. These are then uploaded as JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) data to the Rate my View system. This is an industry-standard data format that allows easy development of new integrations in a wide variety of programming languages and systems. The Application Programming Interface (API) consists of one Representational State Transfer (REST) endpoints, accessible over HTTPS, for downloading a questionnaire, and submitting a response to the system. Another endpoint is available for requesting all responses stored inside the system. These are accessible with a HTTPS GET request to "<http://ratemyview.co.uk/view/>", which returns an array of objects as described Annex 1.

The developer manuals for the app is available on the Github repository:
<https://github.com/paperclipmonkey/Rate-My-View-Android>

5.4.3 Data collection and storage

The Rate My View app collects three types of data:

- Visual data – photos submitted by users
- Spatial data – the locations where the photos were taken
- Survey data – users' responses to the fixed survey questions

All data are primary stored on the RmV server and are easily downloadable for analysis. Downloaded project-related datasets and future research data will be stored in the Ruritage SharePoint site. The visual data is displayed on Ruritage Atlas.

The principles of the Data Management Plan will be followed for all data sets. When downloading the app the user is not required to submit any personal information. The user is also provided with the terms of service for using the, which are as follows:

The Terms of Service

Once submitted photos taken and submitted by Rate my View user are owned by the University of Plymouth and may be used for related website or project work in addition to Rate My View.

5.5 Landscape Connect

Landscape Connect is a mobile phone application (app) that allows in-the-field **user** data collection, combined with a server-based back end that allows real-time data analysis by **researchers and workshop facilitators**. The application collects images and textual data linked to the exact geo-referenced location of the mobile **user**. Textual data is elicited through questionnaires presented to the mobile **user**. The application allows the **researcher** to create their own questionnaires, of any degree of simplicity or complexity, using all conventional survey question types. This is in contrast to RateMyView, which has a set of un-editable questions. The application was developed to be downloaded and used without any fees or licence limitations and is freely available from the Google Play store. The application and server interface are accessible and usable for non-technical users, researchers, and facilitators. The design has the following advantages for User and Researcher Role:

Collected data is uploaded to the server in real time allowing for facilitated workshops where results can be analysed and used for discussions during the course of a workshop. Collected data is cumulative, mapped (geo-located), and downloadable allowing for longer-term data gathering exercises and more complex off-line data analyses. Both the mobile application and server interface are accessible for non-technical **users, researchers, and workshop facilitators**.

Roles within the Application

When using Landscape Connect for participative engagement there are three roles which refer not to person type, but to task being performed (at any given time) in relation to the data collection process:

- **User:** uses mobile application/is a respondent to questionnaire
- **Researcher:** writes questionnaire/collects and analyses data
- **Facilitator:** runs participative data gathering exercise (e.g. a workshop)

Advantages for mobile application User

- Download and installation is similar to other mobile apps – user needs no new knowledge
- The user interface is simple, intuitive, fast and reliable
- The application can be used anywhere allowing on-the-spot data submission
- The application can be used without a mobile signal (replies are uploaded once in signal)
- Individual questionnaires are easy to download using a QR or numerical code
- **Users** can submit multiple copies of the same questionnaire (multiple data instances)

Advantages for Researcher

- App suited to participative engagement allowing **users** (stakeholders) to contribute to objective setting, data analysis, and responses to data findings
- Real-time data collection and mapping allows instant simple analysis/representation
- Questionnaire writing and testing is fast, and changes are easy during the questionnaire building phase
- Data is stored on a secure server – accessible only to **researcher** OR available for download to **users** if required

Advantages for Workshop Facilitator

- App suited to participative engagement allowing **users** (stakeholders) to contribute to objective setting, data analysis, and responses to data findings
- Because data is collated in real-time **facilitators** can discuss emerging results as they upload
- **Users** can instantly see the contributions that they are making to the workshop task/objectives
- Questionnaires can be ground-truthed with **users** allowing refinement in collaboration with **researcher/facilitator**
- With simple on-the-fly analyses (graphs/visual representations) data trends and preliminary findings can be identified and reflected upon

5.5.1 User instructions of mobile application

The user follows a number of simple steps:

1. Install app
2. Open app
3. Download questionnaire (use QR or numerical code)

Figure 5.18 Landscape Connect – user view; (a) questionnaires menu; (b) quick code view; (c) add from code view.

4. Open questionnaire (instance)
5. Take photo (optional)
6. Complete questionnaire (multiple screens)

Figure 5.19 Landscape Connect – questionnaire view (multiple pages).

The figure shows two sequential screenshots of a mobile application interface for a questionnaire titled 'New Landscape'.

Left Screenshot (18:26):

- Header: New Landscape
- Question 1: Are you male or female?
 - Male
 - Female
- Question 2: Which age group are you in?
 - 18-24
 - 25-34
 - 35-44
 - 45-54
 - 55-64
 - 65+
- Question 3: Which of these best describes your current working situation?
 - Employed
 - Self-employed
 - In full time education
 - Temporarily unemployed
 - Unemployed

Right Screenshot (18:27):

- Header: New Landscape
- Question 4: The landscape provides opportunities to gain a sense of heritage / understanding of the past: (Optional)
 - Agree
 - Slightly agree
 - Slightly disagree
 - Disagree
- Question 5: The landscape provides opportunities to be inspired (e.g. for culture, art, design): (Optional)
 - Agree
 - Slightly agree
 - Slightly disagree
 - Disagree
- Question 6: The landscape provides opportunities to learn (e.g. training and research): (Optional)
 - Agree
 - Slightly agree
 - Slightly disagree

7. Submit Questionnaire (multiple times possible per user)
8. Move back to signal (if submissions were made out of signal)

5.5.2 Researchers – Writing questionnaires

1. Log in to Dashboard
2. Go to Questionnaires section
3. Click [New Questionnaire](#) button
4. Use tabs to build questionnaire components:
5. Start – Add metadata
6. Designer – Add questions (in sections/multiple screens)
7. Splash page – Add image and text that **user** will first see
8. Publish – Make finished questionnaire live (available for download to **users**)
9. A published questionnaire can be changed by making a copy and modifying question components
10. A published questionnaire can also be deleted (make sure to download any data before deleting)

Questions need to be carefully formulated, piloted, and refined before any large-scale data gathering exercise (or large workshop). Because of open questionnaire builder format it is tempting to write long complicated questionnaires – this overloads **users** and will reduce both the quality and number of **user** submissions.

Question Tips:

- Not too many (5-10 maximum recommended) – questionnaires should be quick and short
- Required/Optional – Sometimes required questions can be off-putting to the **user**; conversely optional questions may be ignored by the **user**
- Open/Closed – Think about purpose of data; is it investigative/explanatory/confirmatory?
- Single/Multiple line text fields – for open questions and maximum **user** freedom
- Multiple/Single list options – Using lists can limit **user** freedom – think about adding an ‘other comments’ option – but lists of options do simplify and speed up analysis and are better for quantitative graph making from results
- Quantitative/Qualitative – Think about open/closed questions and analysis purposes

Figure 5.20 Landscape Connect –publishing questionnaire view.

5.5.3 Researcher – Managing collected data

1. Log in to Dashboard
2. Go to Questionnaires section

Figure 5.21 Landscape Connect –publishing questionnaire view.

3. Then select a questionnaire to go to **Researcher** collected data view

3. Users download app
4. Users download a questionnaire
5. Users practice completing and submitting questionnaires with the app (trial questionnaire?)
6. Users perform task – use of app for workshop task/purpose (preferably outside singly or in groups)
7. Researcher analyses incoming data (makes an analysis that is immediately comprehensible to users – e.g. averages, trends, surprises, confirmations, etc.)
8. Users/facilitator/researcher reconvene and discuss emerging results/quick analysis
9. Users/facilitator/researcher discuss next steps of participative engagement

5.5.5 Technical Specification

Database: MongoDB database system was used to develop Rate My View. MongoDB differs from traditional relational database systems as it is a document database - chiefly comprised of complex objects allowing a rich data object. MongoDB was selected as it allows very simple schema changes, only being enforced in application code and offers excellent geographical extensions. The software natively supports querying WGS84 lat/long points with complex queries, including geoWithin, allowing database-level support for enforcing geographical constraints on submissions areas.

Server: The server software is written in Node.js, the server-side framework for running JavaScript. It's a feature-complete software library and ecosystem for writing fast performant web servers. It supports for third party library and allows fast-paced development. The server code runs on the Heroku platform, a hosted Platform as a Service (PaaS) system. This system simplifies the maintenance of the system and supports very high uptime requirements as every part of the infrastructure is virtualised.

Interoperability: The Landscape Connect system uses JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) data to download and uploads questionnaires and responses to the Landscape Connect system. This is an industry-standard data format that allows easy development of new users in a wide variety of programming languages and systems. The interface of Landscape Connect was built in a way as to easily facilitate integration in to other platforms, and to allow future extensions. The main Application Programming Interface (API) consists of two Representational State Transfer (REST) endpoints, accessible over HTTPS, for downloading a questionnaire, and submitting a response to the system.

The developer manuals for the app is available on the Github repository:

<https://github.com/paperclipmonkey/Landscape-Connect>

5.5.6 Data collection and storage

Landscape Connect app collects three types of data:

- Visual data – photos submitted by users
- Spatial data – the locations where the photos were taken
- Survey data – users' responses to the variable survey questions

All data are primary stored on the LC server and are easily downloaded for analysis. Downloaded datasets and future research data will be stored in the Ruritage SharePoint site. The principles of the Data Management Plan will be followed for all data sets. When downloading the app the user is not required to submit any personal information. The user is also provided with the terms of service for using the, which are as follows:

The Terms of Service

Once submitted photos taken and submitted by Rate my View user are owned by the University of Plymouth and may be used for related website or project work in addition to Landscape Connect.

5.6 Social Media Tools

The final tool within the My Cult-Rural toolkit is the use of social media mining tools. This is an additional tool that was not identified in the proposal stage of the project. It has been added as it is likely to extend the reach of data available for the co-monitoring programme. The tools allow the analysis of a wider social perspective from the Replicator sites and their actions. The technique will not only make use of posts on social media sites as the locally driven action develop but will use the existing information available on social media sites linked to Replicator sites. The existing information will be used as one of the source of baseline information. The results from the tool will be made available to the Replicators however the tool themselves will not be used by the Replicator due to the level of technical knowledge and software required.

The tool uses R software that includes a package for data visualisation, data manipulation and sentiment analysis. The software allows unstructured text data to be downloaded from Twitter and Instagram. The data is then cleaned using the software and Document Term Matrix is created. The entries of the matrix identifies how many times a word appears in each tweet and hence can be used to calculate word count. This then allows word clouds to be produced. All posts that include a specified “phrase” or “user@” or “topic #” can be accessed. These terms will be identified in consultation with Replicators once action plans and activities have been confirmed.

In addition to word counts a very simple Sentiment Analysis will be undertaken on data collected. The analysis aims to determine whether opinions expressed are positive, negative or neutral. The tool uses the package tidytext to match the posts against a dictionaries of positive and negative words.

5.6.1 Data Collection and storage

All data collected will be downloaded and stored in the Ruritage SharePoint site. The principles of the Data Management Plan will be followed for all data sets.

6. Training and communication

A participatory research approach emphasises the importance of collaboration between researchers and communities in the development and delivery of research programmes and projects that are aimed at directly understanding and responding to the issues that are important to both. In ideal participatory research, participants and researchers co-create the research agenda, process and actions. Both groups also analyse and reflect on the information generated to obtain the findings and conclusions together. A researcher in this context is more a facilitator of the group process than the leader. This approach requires a good understanding of the participatory research dynamic, ethics and reasonable familiarity with the action plan embedded into the research tools. Our training for Replicators reflects the need for an in-depth understanding of participatory research through hands-on experience and personal support available throughout the project.

6.1 Training for using participatory workshop methods

We first introduced My Cult-Rural Toolkit to the Replicators during two sets of workshops:

In the first workshop (Development Workshop at Create, 27-30 May 2019), we invited all Replicators to take part in the Object Mapping workshop as participants. This was intended to introduce the Replicators to the participatory deep workshop methods, the experience of the co-creative data gathering process, and answering research questions. Some of the Replicators were familiar with such techniques, but for some, that was the first experience of this type of community engagement.

The second workshop (Bologna, 26-28 November 2019) was intended to introduce Replicators the remaining tools in the My Cult-Rural Toolkit (Mini-landscapes and Walking Maps) and give them hands-on experience of using these methods in a training situation. Therefore, we dedicated a substantial time to allowing participants to actively lead the research activities (with an emphasis on the Object Mapping workshop that they were already familiar with from the previous workshop) and to share feedback about their experiences with the tools.

Secondly, after the training, we asked Replicators to reflect upon how these methods will match their actions plans (Task 3.3); the activities designed for their communities. To help Replicators to adapt the tools to their unique circumstances we will organise a webinar meeting (allowing for discussion with 2-3 Replicators simultaneously). This webinar will be scheduled before the start of data collection in order to prepare facilitators for their role, check the final preparation of their workshops, data collection strategies and to discuss potential obstacles, difficulties and ethical considerations.

Alongside the workshops and the webinar, Replicators will have access to the supplementary materials at the Digital Hub (description of tools, good practice, discussion forum, etc.). Throughout the lifespan of the project, one-to-one support will be available for all Replicators regarding facilitation of workshops, engagement with communities, and data gathering and analysis.

6.2 Training for using geo-spatial information managements methods (apps)

Both apps, Rate My View and Landscape Connect, were presented to the Replicators at the Development Workshop at Create (27-30 May 2019). For each of apps, we discussed the functionality, the processes of participatory data gathering and possible contexts for use. Further, we prepared a webinar that focuses on practical training in the use of apps and their administrative functionality.

6.3 Communication with the communities

To help Replicators in engaging their local communities with participatory research, we have prepared a collection of good practice advice, and a short video presentation for each of the tools.

Supplementary video materials

Object Mapping: <https://youtu.be/-1gZ8HeoJZY>

Mini-Landscapes: https://youtu.be/F_HBFnOv_9k

Walking Maps: https://youtu.be/h_4kAmUKBNI

For using the Rate My View app to collect data from a variety of stakeholders as they interact with their local landscape (citizens, tourists and visitors to the region) we have prepared a tailored public engagement strategy.

Rate My View – public engagement strategy

- Online visibility – for each of the Replicators we will produce a promotional video that will introduce the app in the context of their local landscape (See local example Rate My View video: <https://youtu.be/JKP5dUZP36M>)
- Postcard – we will design a postcard for each replicator site with basic information about the project and a link to download the app
- Local distribution - postcards, videos and additional information will be distributed across the Replicator region through local accommodation and tourist information centres, targeting both local inhabitants and tourists.

7. Data gathering strategy

Co-monitoring using the My Cult-Rural Toolkit is based on a participatory approach. Data in the form of visual documentation, interviews, surveys and group feedback is collected from participants in varied and diverse contexts. The tools were built with this flexibility of settings and objectives in mind, and designed to be adaptable to the diverse needs of Replicators (and other communities) and varied groups of stakeholders: citizens, policymakers, tourists, etc.

In the context of the Ruritage project, the personalised data gathering strategy has to be carefully fitted with Replicators action plans and objectives (Task 3.3). It will be finalised during the Replicator training mentioned in the Training and Communication section above. Below is the general data gathering strategy with details about the sort of data and target groups for each of My Cult-Rural Toolkit method.

To evaluate the impact of heritage-led interventions developed through the course of Ruritage actions (Task 3.3), we apply a mixed-methods ‘pretest-posttest’ design that combines quasi-experimental quantitative methods and qualitative approaches. In this framework, we identify three main data collection points: pre-test (baseline), mid-test, and post-test, with an additional 4th point of data collection beyond the duration of Ruritage (Figure 7.1)

Figure 7.1 Data collection points for co-monitoring activities using My Cult-Rural Toolkit.

My Cult-Rural Toolkit contains three types of methods (see Introduction) that generate different data outcomes and allows us to engage varied groups of stakeholders. Below we describe each type of tools separately, concerning our research strategy.

7.1 Participatory workshop methods

These methods emphasise local stakeholders' participation and the process of collective knowledge building. They rely on the engagement of participants, producing rich qualitative data outcomes (photos, texts, interviews) and eliciting cultural and perceptual data through hands-on activities. The main limitation is that such an approach is time-consuming both in terms of workshops and data analysis. Hence, we identify Object Mapping as a tool that will be used by all Replicators to establish a baseline and evaluate post-test changes. The other tools will serve as additional methods to answer the replicator-specific research questions. The Table 7.1 presents an initial research plan that will be adjusted to Replicators needs and preferences.

Table 7.1 The use of the participatory workshop methods in the Ruritage co-monitoring process.

Tool	Baseline	Mid-test	Post-test	Follow-up	Data	Target group
Object Mapping	x		x	x	General perception of CES and their benefits (identifies, experiences, capabilities)	Citizens, policymakers, Replicators' active members
Walking Maps	x	x	x	x	Walks focus on topic derived from R's action plans	
Tagspace	x		x		CES benefits identifies, experiences, capabilities	

7.2 Participatory geo-spatial information managements methods

These methods combine the benefits of geographic information systems (GIS) in capturing the spatial distribution of mapped CES, with participatory research methods where participants become the experts in understanding and mapping their own experiences within the landscape. The two mobile apps (RateMyView and Landscape Connect) share the ability to record individual, subjective experience using survey methodology but target different groups.

RateMyView is intended to collect data from a variety of stakeholders interacting with their local landscapes, not only citizens but also tourists and visitors to the region. Therefore, this tool will be used by all Replicators through the lifespan of the project. This will be reflected in advertising campaign material placed in hotel, hostel, B&B and tourist information points, encouraging the use of the app all the visitors.

In comparison, Landscape Connect is intended to support workshop activities with local stakeholders around a particular topic. Landscape Connect allows for the design of surveys tailored to specific research problem, and additionally allows permits initial (real-time) data analysis during workshops. This app is best used as a participatory research tool, where stakeholders share their knowledge, views and collectively

answer their co-created research questions.

Table 7.2 The use of the participatory geo-spatial information management methods in the Ruritage co-monitoring process.

Tool	Baseline	Mid-test	Post-test	Follow-up	Data	Target group
RateMyView	x	x	x	x	photos, GIS, landscape related feedback	Tourists, Citizens
Landscape Connect	x		x	x	photos, GIS, landscape or CES related feedback	Citizens, policy-makers, Replicators active members

7.3 Social media monitoring tools

Social media monitoring tools will capture a broader view of the Replicator landscapes. Our tools for monitoring Twitter and Instagram activity will collate textual and graphic data on how people perceive the landscapes that borders their geographic location through the lifespan of the project. Due to character and the source of this data (public profiles on social media webpages), the collection of such data might have to include additional research points to allow a more gradual understanding of change. The Table 7.3 below presents the minimal number of data collection points.

Table 7.3 The use of the social media monitoring tools in the Ruritage co-monitoring process.

Tool	Baseline	Mid-test	Post-test	Follow-up	Data	Target group
Twitter monitoring tool	x	x	x	x	Text, hashtags, social networks	Public profiles on the related social media accounts in the geographic area of the project
Instagram monitoring tool	x		x	x	Photos, text, hashtags, social networks	

7.4 Data analysis strategy

To analyse collected data, we use a 'pretest-posttest' comparison strategy. The combination of rich qualitative data, GIS and survey-based quantitative data, and finally, a data-mining approach will allow us to evaluate the impact of Ruritage actions on varied levels: individual perception, community and change, and broader social views of the targeted regions; benefiting in development of a comprehensive understanding of the impact of heritage-based interventions. Moreover, the triangulation of research methods will serve as a validity test for qualitative evidence collected during the project.

8. Annex I Rate My View Database Structure

Database

Another endpoint is available for requesting all responses stored inside the system. These are accessible with a HTTPS GET request to "<http://ratemyview.co.uk/view/>", which returns an array of objects as described below.

Rating Response Object

\$schema	http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#
\$id	http://ratemyview.co.uk/response
type	Object
title	A Response Schema
Required	
Properties	

_id
Rating
Age
Knowarea
Display
Ts
Comments
Words
Photo
Loc
Heading

Response ID Schema

\$id	#/properties/_id
type	String
title	The _id Schema
default	
Examples	
pattern	^(.*)\$

5ba7681c62e4e704001c270a

Rating Schema

\$id	#/properties/rating
type	Integer
title	The Rating Schema
default	0
minimum	0
maximum	5

Age Schema

\$id	#/properties/age
type	String
Enum	
title	The Age Schema
description	Age of the respondent
default	
Examples	

0-18
19-24
25-44
45-64
65

Know Area Schema

\$id	#/properties/knowarea
type	String
Enum	
title	The Knowarea Schema
description	How well the respondent knows the area
default	
Examples	

Very well

Not very well

Not at all

Very well

Display Schema

\$id	#/properties/display
type	Boolean
title	The Display Schema
description	Whether the response is displayed on the public website
default	1

Timestamp ID Schema

\$id	#/properties/ts
type	Object
title	The Timestamp Schema
description	Timestamp the image was taken

Comments List Schema

\$id	#/properties/comments
type	String
title	The Comments Schema
default	
Examples	

A nice area

Comment Schema

\$id	#/properties/words
type	Array
title	The Words Schema
Items	

\$id	#/properties/words/items
type	String
title	The Items Schema
examples	

Wonderful weather
Beautiful site
#PolitoSummerSchool

Photo Schema

\$id	#/properties/photo
type	string
title	The Photo Schema
default	
examples	

43F4033A-0A29-4277-AF4B-CE497BBE33B5.jpg
--

Location Schema

\$id	#/properties/loc
type	object
title	The Loc Schema
properties	

type
coordinates

Location Type Schema

type
coordinates

\$id	#/properties/loc/properties/type
type	string
title	The Type Schema
examples	

Point

Location Coordinates Schema

\$id	#/properties/loc/properties/coordinates
type	array
title	The Coordinates Schema
items	

\$id	#/properties/loc/properties/coordinates/items
type	number
title	The Coordinate Schema
default	0
examples	

7.620405
45.137304

Heading Schema

\$id	#/properties/heading
type	integer
Description	The magnetic heading of the device when it took a photo
title	The Heading Schema
default	0

9. Annex II Landscape Connect Database Structure

Database

Questionnaire JSON Object

\$id	https://landscape-connect.com/questionnaire
Type	object
Title	Landscape Connect Questionnaire
description	Schema for a landscape connect questionnaire
Properties	_id
	upload URL
	serverId
	owner
	title
	description
	publicQuestionnaire
	publicData
	introTitle
	introDescription
	website
	introImage
	created
	sections

Upload URL Schema

\$id	#/properties/uploadUrl
Type	string
description	Url on the server for uploading results. This allows potential third-party systems
Examples	

http://landscape-connect.com/api/questionnaires/6E7C6/responses/

\$id	#/properties/serverId
Type	string
Title	The Serverid Schema
description	Unique ID of the questionnaire
Examples	

Serverid Schema

6E7C6

Owner Schema

\$id	#/properties/owner
Type	object
Title	The owner's Id
description	ID of the owner who created the questionnaire
Required	\$oid
Properties	\$oid
Examples	56bf4b5752c5e9110083d334

Title Schema

\$id	#/properties/title
Type	string
Title	The Title
description	The title of the questionnaire which is shown when users download it
Examples	

Ruritage

Description Schema

\$id	#/properties/description
Type	string
Title	The Description Schema
description	The description of the questionnaire. Used to introduce the premise and specifics
Examples	

Heritage for Rural Regeneration. This uses the Landscape Connect technology

\$id	#/properties/publicQuestionnaire
type	boolean
title	The Public questionnaire Schema
description	Whether the questionnaire is displayed publicly on the landscape connect website
default	0
examples	

PublicQuestionnaire Schema

1

PublicData Schema

\$id	#/properties/publicData
type	boolean
title	The Publicdata Schema
description	Whether the questionnaire responses can be publicly downloaded from the landscape connect website
default	0
examples	

1

IntroTitle Schema

\$id	#/properties/introTitle
type	string
title	The Introtitle Schema
examples	

Add new landscape

IntroDescription Schema

\$id	#/properties/introDescription
type	string
title	The Introdescription Schema
examples	

Welcome to the Ruritage questionnaire. Let us walk you through the steps of sharing.

Website Schema

\$id	#/properties/website
type	string
title	The Website Schema
description	A link users can follow for more information on the project

IntroImage Schema

\$id	#/properties/introImage
type	string
title	The Nitroimine Schema
description	A base64 encoded image to be shown when opening the questionnaire
examples	

data:image/jpeg;base64,/EXAMPLE//Z

Created Schema

\$id	#/properties/created
type	object
title	The Created Schema
Example	2016-03-02T23:57:58.942Z

SectionsSchema

\$id	#/properties/sections
type	array
title	The Sections Schema
description	The sections contained inside single questionnaire. Allows breaking up of a questionnaire into logical sections to complete.

Section Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items
type	object
title	The Section Schema
Properties	Questions
	Title

Questions Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/questions
type	array
title	The Questions Schema
items	

Title Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/title
type	string
title	The Title Schema
examples	

Familiarity & Frequency

Question Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/questions/items
type	object
title	A Question
description	An individual question
required	required
	choices
	type
	title

Question Required Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/questions/items/properties/required
type	boolean
title	Required
description	Whether the question needs to be answered to complete the section
default	0
examples	

1

Question Choices Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/questions/items/properties/choices
type	array
title	The Choices Schema
description	Dropdown questions have a selection of possible answers to choose from
items	

Question Choice Items Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/questions/items/properties/choices/items
type	object
title	The Items Schema
properties	

choice

Question Type Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/questions/items/properties/type
type	string
title	The Type Schema
description	The type of question input. Either text, radio, dropdown or photo
examples	radio
	text
	textbox
	photo

Question Title Schema

\$id	#/properties/sections/items/properties/questions/items/properties/title
type	string
title	The Title Schema
description	the question's title displayed to the user
examples	Are you male or female?

10. Annex III My Cult-Rural Toolkit – An introduction to the physical tools.

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

My Cult-Rural Toolkit

An introduction to the physical tools

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465.

About the physical toolkit

What is it?

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit consists of 3 physical tools and 2 digital tools. Tools 1-3 of the toolkit focus on three handmade participatory research tools that use local and raw materials to co-create temporary installations outside. During the co-creation, each tool creates discussion and once made, the installations are recorded using visual and qualitative recording methods. Tools 4-5 are mobile phone application (app) that are free to download and allow text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets.

The three physical tools in the kit

Tool One, Object Mapping, is an outdoor participatory workshop centred on reflective interaction between participants and their landscape. Participants are asked to bring an object related to the area and that means something to them. At the start of the workshop the participants are divided into four groups and invited to create a diagrammatic landscape map using local materials and a grid. On completion of the map, participants are asked to video each other discussing their object. The exercise finishes with the participants mapping their object and again discussing its importance and its location in the map. The exercise involves both participants and facilitators collecting and recording data.

Tool Two, Walking Maps, is a participatory workshop organised around walking shedding light on the interaction between participants, and their embodied and mental reality, and the environment. Walking is here used both as a tool to facilitate an interactive approach to the surrounding, expanding beyond generalised description, and as a metaphor calling for discursive and narrative reflection on the shared questions. Participants are invited to take a walk around the chosen area and collect some materials, objects that caught their eye on the way. A researcher is following the group opening the discussion around the meeting topic. The answers are recorded in relation to location and collected objects. Once the group has completed the walk, they display an exhibition containing the objects, participants' responses and the trace of their trail.

Tool Three, Mini-Landscapes, is a participatory deep workshoping activity that involves participants creating a mini-landscape in an outdoor setting. Participants are divided into groups of four or five and asked to explore the area and produce a mini-landscape in vivarium that represents the group's view of the area. As the task progresses facilitators ask open questions and discuss the process of construction. Towards the end of the task, participants answer these questions by writing only one or two words upon glass slides, and then placing the slides into their mini-landscapes wherever they choose. The mini-landscapes and words are then documented by the facilitators (visually, and/or in transcription).

A guide to delivering each tool

Each tool is broken down in a separate PDF and include:

- Information about the tool
- Difficulty rating
- Number of participants and facilitators
- Time required to prepare, deliver, *document* and tidy up
- Materials needed (including where to source)
- Preparation notes
- Steps you have to take to make the tool
- Open questions you need to ask
- Extra tips

In addition to the three PDFs we have created one more PDF to help facilitators and participants document the visual data. This is 2 pages long and called the 'photo_pocket_book' and can be folded into a small pocket book for quick reference. It contains an area to make a check list and tips on how to make a good photograph.

Each tool is colour coded and named the following way:

<i>Object Circles</i>	cultrural_object_circles.pdf	
<i>Walking Maps</i>	cultrural_walking_maps.pdf	
<i>Mini Landscapes</i>	cultrural_mini_landscapes.pdf	

A note about materials

There are materials that are used across all the tools and materials that are specific to each tool. We are making it easy for you to access the materials.

A note about documentation

i Look out for the blue data icon. It tells you when you need to make data.

Following a workshop, please submit any data (images, videos, transcriptions, etc.) to the **Ruritage SharePoint** site in the correct **Results** folder.

Please note, in tool one participants also submit videos for data analysis.

Good practice

TEN Top Tips

1. Involve the participants in decisions about the topic or theme for activities. Whenever practical, let them decide where you walk and make what you see.
2. Always ask open-ended questions ie those beginning with How? What? Where? These are not leading questions and are great for prompting discussion and encouraging everyone to participate.
3. If you can, have on hand a facilitation team with different skills. You may need a translator. This can be a lot of fun and also make you think carefully about the meaning of words.
4. It is useful to have people with visual and technical skills to help with drawing or visualising ideas that are difficult to articulate.
5. Encourage people who are easily distracted or shy to come forward to start recording visual data using their phones or other devices brought on the day.
6. Use colour: if someone cannot describe what they are feeling, ask them to choose a colour. Don't be scared of letting other sensory feelings emerge such as smell and touch, and record them in any way you can and be ready for emotional responses.
7. Supply small containers for collecting water. Participants might need it to make a water feature or point and it evokes powerful imagery and feelings.
8. Use your surroundings to create atmosphere. If working inside, use lights to create drama. Turn them off if you are asking an open question about the future.
9. Use the Photo Pocket Book to help you and the participants make photographs of the work created. Play with the light. If using glass, angle it to direct reflections; if you have a torch, light up whatever is being discussed or photographed.
10. If you are working with a new community, you need to build trust. We exchanged small locally made gifts, such as sheep's yogurt, seaweed and hand-made biscuits to break the ice.

Help at hand

Do you feel daunted?

You can try different elements with other facilitators if you want to go one step at a time

Contact us for facilitation help? Email:

Tel:

11. Annex IV My Cult-Rural Toolkit – Pocket Photo Guide

My Cult-Rural Toolkit Pocket Book

Make a check list of what to photograph and find tips on how to make a good photograph.

Object Mapping

Walking Map

Mini Landscape

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465.

A "how to photograph" pocket book that you can photocopy back to back, fold up and share. Created by Andy Hughes for TAGSCAPE from an original idea by Ray Wong.

Your subject matter may dictate your choice of framing, your camera might give you framing options...

- SQ
- LAND
- LAND
- PNRV
- PORTRAIT

A camera crops the world as seen by your eyes. The image frame has many conventions: Snap, Format, square, landscape, portrait etc.

*** BASIC SETTINGS ***

Many types of cameras have auto functions. Look on your device/camera and choose 'AUTO'!

When viewing your images look at the screen out of direct sunlight. Use a jacket, coat or similar to create shade.

If your device can view a HISTOGRAM take a look. You should see data along the whole graph.

Are you recording?
Are you interpreting?

COMPOSITION
Follow some rules, break some rules!

What camera do you have?

Take time to learn basic controls

Check each device is fully charged

Keep spare batteries and charger

1. Ensure each lens is 'Clean'!

2. Practice using before workshop

3. How many images will you need?

4. Do you need any other equipment?
TAPED LIGHTING

IMAGE CONVENTIONS
Photographic images exist in many forms. They are widely distributed across the world. However you decide to photograph you could consider this notion...

POCKET PHOTO QUICK GUIDE

CONTENTS

- Choose camera type (P.2)
- Basic camera settings (P.3)
- Subject matter (P.4-5)
- Image conventions (P.6)
- Top tips (P.7)
- Archive/printing (P.8)

PHOTO TOP TIPS

STORING - ARCHIVE - PRINT

Transfer your images to a computer

Backup copy to a usb, cd, or HDisk

Take care to make copies of images
ONE ARCHIVED

Use copies to share, email, print.

Use your preferred editing software to edit images. Remember... email/social media/web use 72ppi printing laser, inkjet, use 200ppi High quality repro, books etc 300ppi

12. Annex V My Cult-Rural Toolkit – Object Mapping Facilitator Guide

Object Mapping

My Cult-Rural Physical Toolkit

© 2019 Andy Hughes

TOOL ONE of The My Cult-Rural Toolkit. Designed and developed to assist and build capacity within Replicator communities to assess the impact of local driven actions. The toolkit employs both ubiquitous technologies and community workshops.

How to Make an Object Mapping

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit consist of 3 physical tools and 2 digital tools. Tools 1-3 of the toolkit focus on three handmade participatory research tools that use local and raw materials to co-create temporary installations outside. During the co-creation, each tool creates discussion and once made, the installations are recorded using visual and qualitative recording methods. Tools 4-5 are mobile phone application (app) that are free to download and allow text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smart-phones or tablets.

What is an Object Mapping?

Tool One *Object Mapping* is an outdoor participatory workshop centred on reflective interaction between participants and their landscape. Participants are asked to bring an object related to the area and that means something to them. At the start of the workshop the participants are divided into four groups and invited to create a diagrammatic landscape map using local materials and a grid. On completion of the map, participants are asked to video each other discussing their object. The exercise finishes with the participants mapping their object and again discussing its importance and its location in the map. The exercise involves both participants and facilitators collecting and recording data.

Difficulty

EASY

Numbers

15-25 participants

Time

BEFORE 20 minutes

DELIVERY 1 hour 15 minutes

AFTER 20 minutes

Materials

- 300cm length x 5cm diameter of ship rope x 2
- Wooden marquee pegs 9 inch x 10
- A5 mini chalk boards x 4
- Black markers Sharpies permanent marker, fine point x 6
- Tote bags or indigenous woven baskets x 15
- Gardening trowels x 15
- Small wooden mallet x 1

Preparation

THREE WEEKS BEFORE

Choose an outside location that is fairly open and at least 7 square metres in size, preferably with one good view of the distance. This space will function as a small 'arena' or 'stage', so think about how you will direct participants around it on the day, and how you will make a visual record of the day with them.

Check the weather forecast for the day. You may want to have a back-up area where participants can make an Object Mapping under cover but a simple open-sided shelter will work best and make the outside feel accessible. If rain is forecast, you may need to pre-collect material but you will still be able to complete the data collection.

Get organised well ahead of the event and collect a fairly wide range of material, such as leaves and waste material, so participants in groups have more than one option to work with.

THE WEEK BEFORE

Give an instruction (see the last section of the PDF) to participants a week before the workshop takes place and re-send them a day or so before the event. This will serve as a reminder and prompt those who haven't to give them some thought.

Choose a space that is a natural stage.

Choose a space that has one view of the distance.

Steps + [Link to video]

STEP 1
Greeting and Setting up the scene

- Introduce the group to the general plan of the activity.
- Check if everyone has brought an object with him or her.
- Walk with your participants to the spot you have chosen to work in.
- Ask two people to put down the rope, crossing the rope so it creates four segments and leaves the feeling of a circle around it.
- Ask two people to write on tent pole pegs the following five times over: intangible, tangible.
- Request that four people write the following on a tent label or mini blackboard each (being careful not to make spelling difficult for someone): Health & Wellbeing, Tourism, Sense of Place and Aesthetic Appreciation. Ask them to hold on to the labels.
- Ask the remainder of people to each take a tote bag and trowel and then to observe the landscape around them for five minutes until the framework of the diagram is set-up.

STEP 2
Dividing into segments

- Ask the four people with the labels to each step forward and choose a segment of the circle, step into it, and hold up what they have written.
- Ask the participants to join one of the circles until each circle has a similar amount of people in.
- Allow participant time for a short discussion about the topic they have chosen.

STEP 3

Building the landscape

- Ask participants to take 25 minutes out in the landscape to find a single material in the landscape that they feel as a group represents the label in their segment. They can use the bags to collect it.

- When each group returns, ask them to fill their segment with their material so it makes a quarter of a circle. If they have not collected enough material to do this, encourage them to collect more.

- Allow time for each group to present about the material they have chosen. Photograph and make a note of what they are describing.

STEP 4

Coming back to personal objects

- As soon as all the segments are filled, ask everyone to work in pairs, perhaps with someone they don't know.

- Ask them to stand around the outside of the circle with their partners. Then ask them to:

- Share their object with each other

- Video each other saying in one or two sentences: What it is and Why they choose it?

- Place their object where they feel it fits on this map and film each other doing this so it is clear where the object has been placed on the circular diagrammatic map

- Ask if each person can also take a photograph of the object on the grid

- Now ask a few of the partners to share their object and what they have said to each other for the whole group. Repeat until you feel the exercise has reached a good ending stage.

! Extra Tips

Two facilitators are needed for a successful workshop to ensure not only that you engage with everyone but also that the task is recorded and results can be discussed afterwards.

Try not to reveal exactly what you are going to do ahead of the day or at the start of the day. Do not show them this PDF or any associated images because you can inadvertently influence the data collection. Let the workshop gradually unfold and explain each element carefully so participants become aware of the layers of the landscape building up in the segments. It's tempting for facilitators to lead too much. If you need to explain something, do it without giving direction, otherwise you will influence what data the participants might collect. This approach will make more sense when you follow it on the day.

Allow an element of performance to emerge (above). Here, a person holds up their object – a spoon – then highlights its meaning by brandishing it amongst a swarm of midges that has surrounded the group.

Welcome serendipity (bottom left). A butterfly landing on the Sense of Place segment is a cause for celebration because it highlights the importance the group attaches to fragrance in the landscape they occupy.

With objects, allow plenty of time so that people can share each other's objects, touch them and ask about them before they record each other.

Remember that the material each group chooses for their segment is as important as the object they bring to the event. Record the information!

Data Collection

i Check you have documented the following information:

- Photograph of the landscape without the personal objects included.
- Closer photograph of each segment.
- Make a note of why each group choose the material they did.

Check the participants have captured the following and that they upload what they have created to you:

- Photographs of personal objects.
- Recordings of interviews related to objects.
- Photograph of each segment with personal objects placed inside.
- Photograph of the whole landscape with the personal object included.

When the event has finished, please add the data you have created to the **Object Mapping Results** folder on **Ruritage Sharepoint** site

www.

Remember to allow time for everyone to:

? Open question - an instruction

A week before the event, give participants the following instruction:

Please bring along an object that you associate with the landscape we will work in and that means something to you. It can be big or small, something you own or have found, or something you've made. A photograph or a phone isn't acceptable.

© Photographs taken by Andy Hughes for the project TAGSCAPE.

My Cult-Rural physical tools were developed by TAGSCAPE.

Object Mappings derive from Object Elicitation, a visual method created for a Global Challenges Research project called Coral Communities. TAGSCAPE was part of this project and through work with an NGO called Mwambao Network, and their experienced facilitators, they co-created Object Elicitation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465.

13. Annex VI My Cult-Rural Toolkit – Walking Maps Facilitator Guide

Walking Maps

My Cult-Rural Physical Toolkit

© 2019 Andy Hughes

TOOL TWO of The My Cult-Rural Toolkit. Designed and developed to assist and build capacity within Replicator communities to assess the impact of local driven actions. The toolkit employs both ubiquitous technologies and community workshops.

How to Make a Walking Map

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit consist of 3 physical tools and 2 digital tools. Tools 1-3 of the toolkit focus on three handmade participatory research tools that use local and raw materials to co-create temporary installations outside. During the co-creation, each tool creates discussion and once made, the installations are recorded using visual and qualitative recording methods. Tools 4-5 are mobile phone application (app) that are free to download and allow text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets

What are Walking Maps?

Tool Two *Walking Maps* is a participatory workshop organised around walking shedding light on the interaction between participants, and their embodied and mental reality, and the environment. Walking is here used both as a tool to facilitate an interactive approach to the surrounding, expanding beyond generalised description, and as a metaphor calling for discursive and narrative reflection on the shared questions. Participants are invited to take a walk around the chosen area and collect some materials, objects that caught their eye on the way. They are asked open questions at key intervals. The answers are recorded in relation to location and collected objects. Once the group has completed the walk, they display an exhibition containing the objects, participants’ responses and the trace of their trail.

Difficulty

MEDIUM

Numbers

5-10

Time

BEFORE 15 minutes

DELIVERY 1 hour and 30 mins

AFTER 15 minutes

Materials

- 5 metre lengths of string x 5 to 10
- 20 A5 see-through bags x 5 to 10 piles
- Wooden washing pegs x 100 to 200
- Black marker pens x 5 to 10
- Indigenous woven or tote bags x 5 to 10
- Landscape Connect loaded onto smart phones or tablets

Preparation

THREE WEEKS BEFORE

Talk to participants well ahead of the event and ask them for suggestions as to where they would like to walk. Give yourself time to consider possible itineraries and how you will plan the walk. Aim for a walk of around 45 minutes in length that is roughly circular so everyone ends up somewhere close to the start point.

Once the walk has been negotiated and finalised, a facilitator needs to do a recce and choose a spot to hang up each group's collection bags. Depending on the size of the group, you will need an area suitable for setting up between three and five washing lines

Choose a pleasant meeting place in the landscape where you can welcome participants and hand out material.

The weather, time of day and location may influence when and where you can install the washing lines. Ideally, choose a spot near to where the walk will finish so everyone can review and take in what they have made together. Plan for adverse weather and have an inside space with room to install the washing lines as back-up.

When setting up the washing lines, be creative and work what is available including trees, poles, posts or columns on a building. Try and keep this hanging area out of sight so the participants don't see it until the end of the walk.

Familiarise yourself with Landscape Connect and check that the open questions for the event are loaded and printed out.

THE WEEK BEFORE

Prepare a kit of materials for each participant consisting of a black marker pen and 15–20 see-through bags. Put these in a tote bag or an indigenous woven basket. Test the app again and calculate how many participants will have access to the app as they walk. Depending on numbers, work out if you need people to collect and answer questions whilst divided into groups. Make sure you have enough washing line and pegs.

Steps

Step 1

Greeting and setting up the walk

- Introduce the group to the general plan of the activity and give each participant a woven or tote bag which includes *their* marker and bags.
- Introduce the general topic for a reflective walk – you can hold a short open discussion about it, but keep it short, the walk will explore the topic.
- Decide if you are going to work together as one group or if you will divide into smaller teams – each group can choose a different route if you feel you have enough facilitators to manage participants and if they know the area.

Step 2

Walk

- Remember to let your participants lead the walk and choose the route. Keep in mind that it shouldn't last more than 45 minutes, and you should end in your final destination - exhibition place.

- As they walk, ask participants to collect materials and place them in their bags, ask them to number the bags as they go.

Step 3

Exploring the deeper meaning

-
 • Once the participants are used to walking and collecting materials, you can start to ask them open questions around your chosen topic. You can record the discussion on a dictaphone, or make some notes.
-
 • Use Landscape Connect app to record the location and document the place where the question is answered. Note its reference number related to the bag that a participant has just used.

Step 4

Setting up the exhibition

- Once you have completed the walk, this is a good time for a short break and a drink. Once rested, ask each person or group to create a washing line by tying strings to a tree or buildings.
- Ask participants to hang the bags on the string using wooden pegs in the order they have collected the objects.
- As the facilitator, you will add a summary of answers to questions you asked doing the walk. Hang your note next to the related object in the bag (use the reference number).
- Discuss with the group collected material and answers.

! Extra Tips

It is best to have three facilitators running this workshop. You need a person at the front and the back of the walk and one to supervise the use of the Landscape Connect App. If getting hold of three is difficult, find some helpers to support the walk so you can concentrate on the App and data collection.

Try to not tell the participants exactly what you are going to do ahead of the day or at the start of the day. Do not show them this document or any associated images because you can inadvertently influence the data collection. Let the workshop unfold naturally and aim to surprise participants with the washing lines at the end of the walk. The advantages of this approach will become clear on the day.

On this walk, we have tried to dispense with a clipboard, dictaphone and GPS unit. The Landscape Connect App collects the textual, digital and geo-referenced data and participants collect physical material. Encourage them to draw or write on the bags if they want to make extra points: this information is also important data.

If people want to walk in a group, let them hang their bags together in a sequence. This means that all the items collected together at a particular spot can be displayed on one peg and numbered 1, 2 etc.,

Leave the bags hanging up for the whole day so other walkers can look at them. Encourage discussion about the Walking Map installation and how the material and the date combine to represent the route and the area you have walked.

Data Collection

Data recording:

- Encourage everyone to take photographs of the installation and have a look at other lines.
- Document each line separately, including the related questions and answers.
- Type up any hand notes once the installation has been taken down.

Open question - an instruction

Open Questions

Check the questions are loaded onto the Landscape Connect app and you've made a note below of what you will ask. *See Tool Five Landscape Connect app to link the two tools together.*

When the event has finished, please add the photographic data you have created to the **Walking Maps Results** folder on **Ruritage Sharepoint site**.

WWW

© All photographs taken by Andy Hughes for the project TAGSCAPE

My Cult-Rural physical tools were developed by TAGSCAPE. An arts-science interdisciplinary project which works to create participatory workshop methodologies to elicit rich data relating to communities engagement with their landscapes.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465.

14. Annex VII My Cult-Rural Toolkit – Mini-Landscapes Facilitator Guide

Mini Landscapes

My Cult-Rural Physical Toolkit

© 2019 Andy Hughes

TOOL THREE of The My Cult-Rural Toolkit. Designed and developed to assist and build capacity within Replicator communities to assess the impact of local driven actions. The toolkit employs both ubiquitous technologies and community workshops.

How to Make a Mini-Landscape

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit consist of 3 physical tools and 2 digital tools. Tools 1-3 of the toolkit focus on three handmade participatory research tools that use local and raw materials to co-create temporary installations outside. During the co-creation, each tool creates discussion and once made, the installations are recorded using visual and qualitative recording methods. Tools 4-5 are mobile phone application (app) that are free to download and allow text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets.

What is a Mini-Landscape?

Tool Three *Mini-Landscape* method is a participatory deep workshopping activity that involves participants creating a mini-landscape in an outdoor setting. Participants are divided into groups of four or five and asked to explore the area and produce a mini-landscape in vivarium that represents the group's view of the area. As the tasks progresses facilitators ask open questions and discuss the process of construction. Towards the end of the task, participants answer these questions by writing only one or two words upon glass slides, and then placing the slides into their mini-landscapes wherever they choose. Mini-landscapes and words are then documented (visually, and/or in transcription).

Difficulty

HARD

Numbers

8-16

Time

BEFORE 30 minutes

DELIVERY 1 hour 45 minutes

AFTER 45 minutes

Materials

- Vivariums x 3 or 4 (Maximum of 4 people per vivarium)
- Gloves x 6 (For people who don't want to touch soil directly)
- Buckets or trays for soil x 5
- Old water containers like small yogurt containers or buckets x 5
- Indigenous woven or tote bags x 8 to 16
- Trowels x 10
- Glass slide x 64 or 124 (8 slides per person)
- Glass chalk pens, white x 8 to 16
- A small torch

Preparation

THREE WEEKS BEFORE

Finalise your choice of location for the event – ideally an outside space with links to the open questions you are going to ask and that may also help to stimulate discussion on the day. Choose somewhere open where you can place five glass vivariums – transparent containers to put living plant material in. It should function as a natural 'stage' that you can move around freely, and feel welcoming when your participants arrive.

Think about how the weather forecast will affect the space and whether you might need to go inside or under shelter owing to bad weather or heat. Try to make the most of daylight hours by starting at dawn, or maybe staying until dusk.

Choose a space outside that you can use as a stage. You will be greeting participants here and want them to feel welcome as well as relaxed.

You may want to have a back-up area for inside working if it's impossible to be outside, but try to ensure the outside still feels accessible. You may need to pre-collect material if the weather forecast is set for rain – buckets are useful for this task – but you can still complete the data collection. Any inside working space should look attractive with plenty of material for making the Mini-Landscapes, including soil, plants and leaf litter.

Advise participants that they will need to wear old clothes and provide gloves for those who prefer not to handle soil and plants.

Reading from pieces of paper can interrupt the flow so start to familiarise yourself with the open questions that you will paste into the back of this document and commit as many as you can to memory.

ONE THE DAY

Set up the site so everything is ready to go when the participants arrive. Position the 5 vivariums with a toolkit made up of bags and trowels beside each one and make sure your own toolkit is complete. Have your slides and pens counted out, with this document as back-up. Leave one facilitator on site if the participants have to be collected.

Steps + [link to video]

Step 1

Gathering and greeting

- Welcome the whole participant group and introduce the purpose and plan for the workshop.
- Participants each introduce themselves with their name and 1-3 sentence description of a place of personal significance or meaning (e.g. a favourite walk, viewpoint, secret place, etc.).
- One facilitator leads the whole group in short (10mins) familiarisation walk through the workshop landscape. During introduction be aware that what is said at this point might skew results collected later.. If the workshop group know the location well, they could describe the terrain themselves on this walk.

Step 2

Building landscapes in smaller groups

- Explain that five subgroups (of 2-4 people per vivarium) will each construct their own mini-landscape.
- Split the workshop into the 3 to 4 subgroups – some pairings might choose to work together.
- Ask each subgroup what kind of mini-landscape they think they might like to make – vivariums can contain abstractions, simulations or more literal representations of the surrounding workshop landscape. Participants should be encouraged to discuss together what they would like to make.
- Explain that each subgroup has 1hr to collect and arrange materials to fill a vivarium with a mini-landscape.
- Explain that each subgroup can place their vivarium wherever they would like in the workshop terrain (being careful how to carry).
- Explain that facilitators will visit them as time proceeds to help or advise.
- Explain that during the making process each subgroup will be asked some questions about their mini landscape.

Step 3
Set open questions (record open data)

- Once each subgroup is well on the way to making their vivarium (at least 1/2hr) give each person in the subgroups a set of 8 slides and 8 glass chalk pens.

- i** • Whilst distributing slides and pens facilitators set a couple of open questions.
 - Explain that questions are to be answered in only 1-2 words per slide. Ask them to number the slides in the order they are asked.
 - Encourage each subgroup to choose the most significant slides they would like to display in or around their vivarium.**
- Spread the task of materials distribution and question-setting between the two facilitators.
- If there is a third facilitator they might be tasked with documenting the emerging mini-landscapes and participants in the process of making vivariums photographically, paying attention to capturing slide answers, especially those placed in and around vivariums.

Step 4
Close workshop

- Move the vivariums close enough that they can all be seen together by whole group. (Again, be careful how they are carried especially as now heavier.)
- Ask all the participants to examine and look into each of the 5 vivariums.
- Ask each subgroup to summarise their own mini-landscape to the whole workshop group.
- Allow an opportunity for discussion and shared thoughts about the workshop process.

- i** • Encourage participants (as well as facilitators) to make photographs, since mini-landscapes will be dismantled (See Photo Pocket Book tips: e.g. to get close-ups of the mini-landscapes participants could lie down if the ground is not wet or hard).*
- Close workshop and thank participants.

! Extra Tips

Assign two facilitators to run the workshop. This will ensure that everyone is involved, the task is recorded, and that results can be discussed afterwards. For workshops with participants numbering more than 12, it's best to engage a third facilitator.

Try to not tell the participants exactly what you are going to do ahead of the day or at the start of the day. Do not show them this document or the images that go with it because you can inadvertently influence the data collection. Let the workshop gradually unfold, while explaining each element carefully, so that everyone is involved in the process and you or the other facilitators don't lead them in a particular direction. This approach will make more sense when you follow it on the day.

This workshop requires everyone to focus, think about what they are doing, and interact as a group. Make people feel comfortable by providing a welcome drink and snack. At this woodland event, we had a fire and everyone enjoyed hot chocolate.

If there is time, and you feel some participants need to orientate themselves better within the space, walk for 10 minutes before the participants are divided into smaller groups.*

For elderly participants or those with disabilities, provide a chair and put the vivariums on a table. Check your table won't wobble and the ground is flat.**

People often want to collect water so take along a supply of empty yogurt pots or small buckets.

You can still create extraordinary landscapes in the rain but check everyone is well prepared for such an eventuality and have somewhere dry where you can exhibit them afterwards. If it's very hot, provide umbrellas!

Data Collection

Data recording:

- Photograph of each landscape with slides included.
- Close ups of slides to capture their placement and record the answers on slides.
- Recording of group summaries about their landscapes.

Following the workshop, please submit any data (images, videos, transcriptions, etc.) to the **Ruritage SharePoint** site in the **Mini Landscape Results** folder. Words from the slides will need to be transcribed and submitted as a text-based document, along with photographic images of the slides and the complete vivariums; which when possible clearly indicate the in-vivarium location of each slide.

Remember to allow time for everyone to:

Open questions

A week before the event, paste the 8 open questions you have been sent here:

© All photographs taken by Andy Hughes for the project TAGSCAPE bar images *Jason Parsons and images **Alan Stewart

My Cult-Rural physical tools were developed by TAGSCAPE. An arts-science interdisciplinary project which works to create participatory workshop methodologies to elicit rich data relating to communities engagement with their landscapes.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465.

15. Annex VII My Cult-Rural Toolkit – Rate My View Facilitator Guide

RATE MY VIEW

My Cult-Rural DIGITAL Toolkit

TOOL FOUR of The My Cult-Rural Toolkit. Designed and developed to assist and build capacity within Replicator communities to assess the impact of local driven actions. The toolkit employs both ubiquitous technologies and community workshops.

How to Use Rate My View

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit consist 3 physical tools and 2 digital tools. Tools 1-3 of the toolkit focus on three handmade participatory research tools that use local and raw materials to co-create temporary installations outside. During the co-creation, each tool creates discussion and once made, the installations are recorded using visual and qualitative recording methods. Tools 4-5 are mobile phone application (app) that are free to download and allow text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets.

What is Rate My View?

Rate My View is a mobile phone application (app) that allows in-the-field data collection, combined with a server-based back end that allows real-time data analysis. The app is free to download and allows text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets. It uses GPS technology to pinpoint the users location and also detects the direction the user is facing. Images and text are cached on user's devices and then automatically uploaded to the Rate my View website when WIFI or phone signal are available.

Difficulty

It's EASY, QUICK and GOOD FUN

Numbers

UNLIMITED - advertise it - display RATE MY VIEW leaflets and your postcards. Plus use: #RateMyView

Time

BEFORE Download takes less than 5 mins

ON THE DAY Using the app takes less than 5 mins

AFTER We do the analysis but you keep an eye on the back-end

Follow these easy steps:

DOWNLOAD the App. from www.ratemyview.co.uk

TAKE A PHOTO of a view that you like or is important to you.

RATE your view - up to 5 stars

COMPLETE 3 PHRASES (required) which describe the view and in the comments box – please provide further information on the reasons why this particular view is important to you, these comments can be either positive or negative. Note you can submit as many views as you like!

UPLOAD your Image – Please note this will only happen when you have WiFi coverage however your phone will remember the co-ordinates and direction of view.

The Uploaded image will then appear on the map for Everyone to see. By taking part and rating your view you will be providing us valuable information about the importance of our landscape and what it means to you.

Use on smart phones.

Use on tablets.

The App Dashboard

Follow these steps for behind the scenes work

DASHBOARD

Login to Dashboard with web browser (Best with Google Chrome/Mozilla Firefox) at:

www.ratemyview.co.uk/admin

The Dashboard gives an overview of recently submitted views in your submission area as statistics, and as map locations.

Move between different back end screens with tabs.

AREAS

The Areas screen shows all submission areas in the system.

Click the right hand side of the screen to change a submission area's twitter handle or website address.

Hover the mouse over the icon at the bottom left of the screen to change the basemap between Terrain/Satellite layers.

VIEWS

The Views screen allows all submitted views in a submission area to be reviewed.

To filter all views in a submission area use the drop-down list in the Search box at top left of the views screen.

Click any map to the left hand side of each view to see the map of all views in this submission area.

DOWNLOAD

Click the Download button at the top right of the views screen to download all views data from this submission area.

Data can be downloaded as Google Earth/GIS layer (.kmz file), images (.jpgs), or as data for use in Excel (.csv).

The App Dashboard continued

EDIT VIEW

To edit a submitted view click on the image to the right hand side of the views screen.

The Edit View screen will open.

This screen allows moderators to correct any view details (headings, spellings, etc.)

The exact GIS location marker can be moved in the edit view page. Click Location tab, then drag the GOS marker to a new position on the map/satellite view.

HIDE FROM THE PUBLIC

Moderators can temporarily hide any view from the public website should it contain content that violates the Terms of Service.

If necessary these views can be deleted by the moderator.

To hide a view click the checkbox near the bottom of the edit view screen.

Make Notes

Get your postcard printed! Supply the Toolkit team with an image of your landscape. We will then supply a file to print.

Then distribute to Hotels, Cafes, visitors centres and guest houses.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465.

16. Annex V My Cult-Rural Toolkit – Landscape Connect Facilitator Guide

LANDSCAPE CONNECT

My Cult-Rural DIGITAL Toolkit

PART FIVE of The My Cult-Rural Toolkit. Designed and developed to assist and build capacity within Replicator communities to assess the impact of local driven actions. The toolkit employs both ubiquitous technologies and community workshops.

How to Use Landscape Connect

The My Cult-Rural Toolkit consist 3 physical tools and 2 digital tools. Tools 1-3 of the toolkit focus on three handmade participatory research tools that use local and raw materials to co-create temporary installations outside. During the co-creation, each tool creates discussion and once made, the installations are recorded using visual and qualitative recording methods. Tools 4-5 are mobile phone application (app) that are free to download and allow text and images to be collected and georeferenced using smartphones or tablets.

What is Landscape Connect?

Landscape Connect is a mobile phone application (app) that allows in-the-field user data collection, combined with a server-based back end that allows real-time data analysis by researchers and workshop facilitators.

The application collects images and textual data linked to the geo-referenced location of the mobile user.

Textual data is elicited through questionnaires presented to the mobile user. The researcher can create questionnaires of any degree of simplicity or complexity, using the main conventional survey question types.

Collected data is uploaded to the server in real time allowing for facilitated workshops where results can be analysed, and used for discussions during the course of a workshop.

Collected data is cumulative, mapped (geo-located), and downloadable allowing for longer-term data gathering exercises and more complex off-line data analyses.

Follow these easy steps:

Both the mobile application and server interface are accessible for non-technical users, researchers, and workshop facilitators. The application is free to download and use without costs or licence limitations.

Install app (<http://landscape-connect.com/>)

Open app

Download questionnaire (use phone camera and QR code or enter numerical code)

Open questionnaire (instance)

Take photo (optional)

Complete questionnaire (multiple screens)

Submit Questionnaire (multiple times possible per user)

Move back to mobile signal (if submissions were made out of signal)

Use on android smart phones and tablets.

Use in group workshops.

Researchers - Writing questionnaires

1. Log in to Dashboard
2. Go to Questionnaires section
3. Click button
4. Use tabs to build questionnaire components:
 - a. Start – Add metadata
 - b. Designer – Add questions (in sections/multiple screens)
 - c. Splash page – Add image and text that user will first see
 - d. Publish – Make finished questionnaire live (available for download to users)
5. A published questionnaire can be changed by making a copy and modifying question components
6. A published questionnaire can also be deleted (make sure to download any data before deleting)

Questions need to be carefully formulated, piloted, and refined before any large scale data gathering exercise (or large workshop). Because of open questionnaire builder format it is tempting to write long complicated questionnaires – this overloads users and will reduce both the quality and number of user submissions.

Question Tips:

- Not too many (5-10 maximum recommended) – questionnaires should be quick and short
- Required/Optional – Sometimes required questions can be off-putting to the user; conversely optional questions may be ignored by the user
- Open/Closed – Think about purpose of data; is it investigative/explanatory/confirmatory?
- Single/Multiple line text fields – for open questions and maximum user freedom
- Multiple/Single list options – Using lists can limit user freedom – think about adding an ‘other comments’ option – but lists of options do simplify and speed up analysis and are better for quantitative graph making from results.
- Quantitative/Qualitative – Think about open/closed questions and analysis purposes

Researcher - Managing collected data

1. Log in to Dashboard
 2. Go to Questionnaires section
- Then select a questionnaire to go to Researcher collected data view

4. View results: GIS locations on map, user images (below map), and question responses (downloadable as data files)

Facilitator - Workshop example format

1. Facilitator introduces workshop task/
purpose
2. Facilitator introduces app
3. Users download app
4. Users download a questionnaire
5. Users practice completing and
submitting questionnaires with the app
(trial questionnaire?)
6. Users perform task – use of app for
workshop task/purpose (preferably
outside singly or in groups)
7. Researcher analyses incoming
data (makes an analysis that is
immediately comprehensible to users
– e.g. averages, trends, surprises,
confirmations, etc.)
8. Users/facilitator/researcher
reconvene and discuss emerging
results/quick analysis
9. Users/facilitator/researcher discuss
next steps of participative engagement

Plus!

**You use Landscape Connect
in Tool Three, Walking Maps.**

Connect with other #LandscapeConnect users

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465.